

MANAGEMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES MODERN CHARACTERISTICS OF PROCESSES

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Аннотация: Мақолада шлаб чиқариш корхоналари фаолиятини модернизациялаш ва диверсификация қилишни бошқаришнинг мазмуни ва замонавий хусусиятларига илмий қарашларни тадқиқ этиш, шу асосда унинг моҳияти ва жиҳатларини аниқлашга қаратилган жараёнлар ёритилган.

Калитли сўзлар: иқтисодий ислохотлар, иқтисодиётни модернизация қилиш, диверсификациялаш, иқтисодиёт тармоқлари, барқарор иқтисодий ўсиш, ишлаб чиқариш корхоналари, фаолиятни модернизациялаш, диверсификация қилиш, бошқариш мазмуни, замонавий хусусиятлар, илмий қарашлар.

Аннотация: В статье освещаются на основе определения сущности и процесса исследования научные взгляды содержание и современные особенности управления модернизации и диверсификации деятельности производственных предприятий.

Ключевые слова: экономические реформы, модернизация экономики, диверсификация, отрасли экономики, устойчивый экономический рост, производственные предприятия, модернизация деятельности, диверсификация, содержание управления, современные черты, научные взгляды.

Annotation: The article highlights, based on the definition of the essence and the research process, the scientific views, the content and modern features of the management of the modernization and diversification of the activities of industrial enterprises.

Key words: economic reforms, modernization of the economy, diversification, sectors of the economy, sustainable economic growth, manufacturing enterprises, modernization of activities, diversification, management content, modern features, scientific views.

Enter. In the framework of economic reforms, economic modernization and diversification programs implemented in our country during the years of independence, stable economic growth of economic sectors is ensured. In this regard, special attention was paid to increasing the effectiveness of strategic management in diversifying the activities of production enterprises. Today, there are problems in the industry that are waiting for their solution, among them, one of the urgent issues is to accelerate the organization of production based on modern high technology that meets the requirements of the world standard and ensures the production of exportable products. In the Development Strategy for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, the important tasks of deepening the structural changes, modernization and diversification of the leading sectors of the national

economy are defined. Effective implementation of these tasks requires the acceleration of work on expanding the assortment of production products and increasing export potential in industrial enterprises of our country, in particular, in manufacturing enterprises.

The developed countries of the world, especially in countries such as the USA, Germany, Great Britain, Japan, South Korea, France, are managing to eliminate the crisis processes in their national economies based on the diversification of production, increase the purchase demand, and strengthen the competitiveness of their national products in the world market. At present, the strategy of reducing the risk of a crisis and the production movement of diversification is being introduced as the priority direction of production diversification management in industrial enterprises, especially in the manufacturing industry. In order to achieve competitiveness, scientists achieved important scientific results, first of all, on the structural change and diversification of the economy, the development of production based on high technologies.

Analysis and method. The essence of diversification in the industrial network is that it allows enterprises with different organizational and legal forms of ownership to adapt to the conjuncture of specialized markets where demand and supply change dramatically.) is understood to include products (services) that are not directly similar.

Reasons that encourage enterprises to produce new products (to provide new services) and to enter new markets with them can be: to leave depressed markets of the given sector and enter sectors with higher profit rates, to reduce risks and to receive financial benefits. At the heart of diversification are objective reasons: obtaining economic benefits from combined production, in which tendencies to combine its various processes, stages and types are realized.

Diversification of the activities of production enterprises should include the production of new products (services):

- using new technologies. The new product is aimed at the consumers of the enterprise or is released together with the product produced at the same time (horizontal diversification);
- using the existing technology, a new product improved on the basis of the current technology is produced (centralized diversification);
- production that is technologically unrelated to the product being produced at the same time (conglomerate diversification).

Production enterprises were recommended to organize diversification in two different directions depending on the level of availability of financial opportunities: in the first direction, diversification according to the main type of activity should be carried out step by step; in the second direction, on the contrary, the diversification strategy should not be related to the main production.

In the research, it was determined that the need to diversify production in manufacturing enterprises is determined by various factors. In addition, achieving the goal of diversification depends primarily on the financial capabilities of the country at the macro level, and of enterprises and firms at the micro level (Table 1).

The leader of the economy in Uzbekistan perform networks It should be noted that the indicators of development are primarily aimed at maintaining high and consistent growth rates and further strengthening of macroeconomic stability. It refers to the

departure of the production enterprise from the current activity and its transition to new areas diversification strategy seeing released

This is it of the process success a lot in terms of work release enterprise for relatively internal and external environment how much thorough to what has been learned depends. Such the analysis directions work release in the enterprise diversification strategic manage implementation on the basis of research and determination of factors affecting processes must.

Table 1

Work release industry enterprises diversification to do factors

Technician and technological	Economical	Financial	Social	Strategic
1. Production powers complete work provide and develop output potential save to stay 2. raw materials, materials, from technology of use alternative options. 3. Unemployment and of resources complete use level.	1. Capital traditional in networks excess accumulated stay and him to spend new fields to determine 2. In the market weight increase, new markets take over 3. To a synergistic effect reach 4. Scale the effect provide. 5. of resources limited. 6. Saving resources policy.	1. Danger is danger and risk taking level decrease 2. Financial stability. 3. Financial potential increase	1. Work er personnel save to stay 2. New job places create 3. Other needs satisfy 4. Manager-of innovative policy.	1. Market conjunctural a his to vibrations adaptation. 2. Insurance effective gini increase 3. Antimonopoly legislation. 4. State order. 5. Prospective plans designation.

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Diversification done work release industry in enterprises managers business strategy taking into account the purpose of the organization - different of the enterprise Multidisciplinary for the different departments operating in the networks strategic movement the plan work outputs must Work release enterprises of diversification organizational strategy to the theory in reliance diversification organizational activities aimed at creating conditions that ensure the achievement of goals complex done need to increase.

Organizational development strategies can be divided into types in order to change the micro- and macro-economic conditions, which can be adapted to the specific situation, for the production enterprises to occupy an optimal position in the diversification market.

Table 2

Production enterprises within the organizational levels of management strategic measures of diversification

Strategy level	Diversification to do with depends strategic measures
1. Corporate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high productive farm portfolio create and management; • structural units achieving synergism between and him competitiveto advantage rotate; • investment priority directions designation and corporate resources of activity the most attractive to the fields orientation.
2. Entrepreneurship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to strengthen competitiveness directed measures work exit; • external in the environment to changes answer return mechanismsforming; • main and functional of divisions strategic actionscombine; • of the enterprise to himself special issues and problems solution to do according toeffort set.
3. Functional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • field managers to review, revise andcombine • the only one actions the plan work exit; • workers qualification increase and again teaching; • operational risks forecasting.

The methods of applying strategic management to the management of diversification processes of production industry enterprises, the method of justifying production diversification strategies in branch enterprises with the method of organizational-economic balance of forces are methodologically justified.

Summary. It was proposed to consider the processes of managing the diversification of the activities of manufacturing enterprises in the form of the balance of organizational and economic forces, dividing the internal and external economic environment into its components (economic, production, technological, innovative, management, social) in the form of "environment - asset - passive".

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